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Research Article

**RECOGNITION AND DOMINATION OF IDIOPATHIC
VENTRICULAR FIBRILLATION CONGENITAL
CONTINGENT ON PROFESSIONAL DANGERS**

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Abstract:

Electrophysiological inspection showed a low tachycardia outline, and the victim was advised to avoid the consumption of certain medicines and drug abuse in victims with Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation congenital. The ECG showed an electrocardiographic outline in which Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation kind- 2 congenital was stated and the victim was sent to a circulatory tachycardia cure center, where flecainide confirmed the conclusion. Polymorphic ventricular tachycardia is caused by vasovagal and unexpected demise. These electrocardiographic symbols may appear during a routine professional inspection of an asymptomatic victim. Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation congenital is renowned by fainting or unexpected demise based on the electro-cardio graphic outline of ST segment advancement in the normal heart, but on the precordial paths from V1 to V3 and the right bundle division block.

Keywords: *Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation Congenital, Professional Dangers, Recognition, Domination.*

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CASE REPORT:

The ECG showed an electrocardiographic outline in which Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation kind- 2 congenital was stated and the victim was sent to a circulatory tachycardia cure center, where flecainide confirmed the conclusion. A 37-yrs-old man with a history of vasovagal or vasovagal has joined a professional medical service for routine monitoring. Experts conducting scheduled tests can detect Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation congenital and prevent unexpected demise. It is important to understand the professional threat of an employee who is diagnosed with Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation congenital to prevent or reduce the occurrence of ventricular tachycardias. The victim remains asymptomatic 6 months after conclusion. Conclusions. Electrophysiological inspection showed a low tachycardia outline, and the victim was advised to avoid the consumption of certain medicines and drug abuse in victims with Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation congenital.

INTRODUCTION:

It is renowned by a typical electrocardiographic outline and susceptibility to ventricular tachycardias and unexpected demise in normal precordial leads. The band Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation (BS) was first described in 1992.

1. In recent yrs, many contributing genetic mutations have been identified, some mechanisms concomitant with the appearance of the characteristic phenotype have been clarified, and progress has been made in identifying clinical prognostic markers. Three BS concomitant electrocardiographic outlines have been identified. Kind- 1 outline (Fig. 1) is renowned by a convex ST height of 2 mm ST segment, followed by negative T waves in many exact precordial cables (V1-V3)⁶. The kind- 2 outline is explained by an elevated concave elevation of the ST segment by about 2 mm in the right precordial lead, followed by positive T waves or iso-phases showing an assisting ECG outline.

2. BS is caused by a large irregularity of the myocardium ion channels and is determined by genetic mutations without being concomitant with any structural heart disease.

Fig 1. – 12-lead ECG showing an outline of spontaneous kind- 1 Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation congenital in leads V1 and V2 (diagnostic).

Kind- 1 formula is the only model accepted as a conclusion. Kind- 3 model (Figure 2) is defined as any of the above, with the segment height ST <1 mm. BS diagnostic confirmation requires the development of kind- 1 pattern. Kind- 2 and 3 outlines are significant, but BS are not analytical and require a positive result for the presence of ajmaline or flecainide, i.e.

Fig 2. 12-lead ECG showing a kind- 3 outline Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation congenital in the exact precordial leads (suggestive, not diagnostic).

This requires that all victims with a characteristic ECG outline are isolated at threat even when they are isolated. We present the case of BS detected during the vocational exam. Victims with BS remain largely asymptomatic, but fainting or unexpected demise occurs at any time due to up to 25% of ventricular tachycardias (torsade de pointes and / or ventricular fibrillation).

A CASE REPORT:

There were no fainting or unexpected demise in the family. For eight yrs he worked at a company manufacturing wood cutting machines, the main threat of industrial hygiene was exposed to noise, cutting oils and chlorinated solvents (methylene

chloride and trichloroethylene) used for cleaning. The victim was a 37-yr-old man who smoked nine cigarettes a day and 70 cigarettes for 22 yrs ago, but is currently undergoing smoking cessation therapy and there is no history of alcohol or other substance abuse. bodybuilding and diving. The ECG detected a high increase in the segment of the saddle ST 2 in the left pre-moon hemisphere and the right precordial lead (Fig. 3) (kind- 3). In a routine professional inspection, the fleshly inspection was satisfactory, plasma pressure was 120/70 mmHg, and total cholesterol 318 mg / dl (LDL: 150 mg / dl) and triglycerides 254 mg / dl in plasma counts. He also worked as a security guard, where from time to time he was exposed to very stressful situations.

Fig 3. ECG of the victim stated here, showing a kind- 2 outline Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation congenital (in V2: concave ST segment elevation > 2 mm followed by isodiphasic saddle back outline T wave).

To complete the threat classification, electrophysiological studies were first performed showing normal conduction intervals, and secondly, continuous ventricular tachycardias were not induced during the ventricular pacing protocol. The employee was sent to a referral center for circulatory tachycardias and underwent a flecainide test to detect high-quality clinical tolerance confirming the conclusion of BS and the transition from model 2 to kind- 1. Since reports show that fever can cause ventricular tachycardias in victims with BS, it is recommended to avoid energy cure with medicines and addictive substances and any feverish diseases and medicines listed in the table with the necessary consultation in case of vasovagal. Therefore, the victim was assessed to have a low tachycardia threat outline (asymptomatic, non-diagnostic ECG without induction in an electrophysiological study). Six months later the victim remained asymptomatic. An appointment was made for genetic tests and check-ups at a cardiology out-victim clinic.

DISCUSSION:

Channelopathy is simply an electrical disorder and is usually not concomitant with any underlying structural heart disease 4. BS is in a set of heart diseases called channelopathies, diseases caused by abnormalities concomitant with the formation of

cellular action potential in transmembrane ion channels, the most serious consequence is a predisposition to malignant ventricular tachycardias. The estimated incidence of BS is 5/10,000 people, but this number probably underestimates the true incidence because many victims may have silent forms of the disease. BS is expected to increase from 4 to 12% of all unexpected expiries and 20% of unexpected expiries⁹. They happen in a seemingly normal heart. Current indications for ICD implantation are recommended by the Second International Consensus BS. Implantable cardioverter-defibrillator (ICD) is the only cure that prevents unexpected demise in BS. Victims with symptomatic BS (unexpected fainting, unexpected demise stopped) and asymptomatic victims in whom electrophysiological inspection causes continuous ventricular tachycardias, especially spontaneous. We also recommend aggressive fever management, emergency consultations in the event of unexpected loss of consciousness, and regular monitoring by a cardiologist. ECG outlines are considered candidates for ICD implantation. Regardless of the level of threat of tachycardia, it is recommended for all victims diagnosed with BS to avoid certain medicines and various medicines (Table I; full list is available at www.Idiopathicventricularfibrillationmedicines.org).

Main medicaments and substances of abuse that should be evaded in people with Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation disease*		
Medicament	Antiarrhythmics	Propafenone Procainamide Ajmaline Pilsicainide Flecainide
	Psychotropic agents	Desipramine Amitriptyline
		Nortriptyline Trifluoperazine Clomipramine Loxapine Lithium
		Anaesthetics
	Others	Ergonovine Acetylcholine
Substances of abuse	Cocaine Alcohol	

* Changed by: Wolpert C, Postema PG, Amin AS *et al.* victims and Medicines with Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation congenital: literature review, approvals and updated website (www.Idiopathicventricularfibrillationmedicines.org). Heart rate in 2009; 6: 1335–41.

This means that workers exposed to these substances may have an increased threat of unexpected expiry if they have BS. In addition, fleshly factors such as electricity or extremely stressful professions, such as elite athletics or football, may support the occurrence of tachycardias and or conduction disorders and may be discouraging in this victim group. Biological, fleshly and chemical hazards in the workplace can lead to circulatory conduction disorders. Table II first describes the main chemicals that can cause tachycardias, as well as those that can cause toxic hyperthermia.

Table II. Main professional threat concomitant with the development of circulatory tachycardias

Main professional threat concomitant with the development of circulatory tachycardias		
Toxic agents	Chlorinated solvents	Methylene chloride Trichloroethylene Tetrachloroethylene Methyl chloroform
	Heavy metals	Antimony
	Organophosphate insecticides	Chlorpyrifos
	Freons	Chlorodifluoromethane
Fleshly agents	Electricity	Exposure above 30 mA
	High temperatures	Polymer fume fever. Heat stress. Metal fume fever (Zn, Cu, Cd, Mg).
Others	Highly-stressful situations.	

In occupations with threat outlines, as described in Table II, the inclusion of ECGs in medical dominations may help in the early recognition of BS, but additional sensitivity, specificity and predictive value testing will be required. ECG is useful in detecting electrocardiographic abnormalities concomitant with unexpected demise, as in the case of BS.

CONCLUSION:

Polymorphic ventricular tachycardia is caused by vasovagal and unexpected demise. These electrocardiographic symbols may appear during a routine professional inspection of an asymptomatic victim. Idiopathic ventricular fibrillation congenital is renowned by fainting or unexpected demise based on the electro-cardio graphic outline of ST segment advancement in the normal heart, but on the precordial paths from V1 to V3 and the right bundle division block.

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